

Idiomatic Correctness-Checking via Julienne in Fortran 2023

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Abstract—This paper presents a unified approach to unit testing and runtime assertion checking using Fortran 2023. The paper describes the support for our approach in the **Julienne** framework. Julienne leverages recent Fortran standards to implement object-oriented design patterns, support testing parallel programs, and implement functional programming patterns in order to craft idioms inspired by natural-language expressions. The presented idioms employ novel operators to write expressions that evaluate to a test-diagnosis object encapsulating two components: (1) the test outcome or assertion outcome and (2) an automatically generated diagnostic string. Two other novel aspects of the approach include (1) the ability to enforce assertions inside pure procedures and (2) the ability to output rich diagnostic information inside pure procedures during error termination when assertions fail. The latter capability mitigates against a reason that Fortran programmers commonly cite for not writing pure procedures: difficulty obtaining useful program output inside pure procedures when debugging code. This paper demonstrates how the adoption of the proposed idioms leads naturally to a unifying theme across two otherwise disparate technologies: unit testing and runtime assertion checking. Finally, this paper describes the usage of the Julienne testing framework for writing unit tests and assertions in the Matcha high-performance computing application and the Fiats deep learning library.

Index Terms—Unit testing, runtime assertion checking, Fortran, high-performance computing, deep learning

I. INTRODUCTION

A. Motivation and Background

1) *Overview*: Efforts to ensure software correctness range from mathematically formal methods for specifying and proving correctness to informal strategies for externally testing isolated software units or internally checking logical assertions about program state. The rigor and complexity required in formal methods typically places such methods beyond the reach of research software engineers with minimal training in computer science. Arguably the most accessible formal method for those without a deep background in the subject involves using the Object Constraint Language (OCL) [1, 2] to formally specify constraints on program state in Unified Modeling Language (UML) diagrams [3]. Such constraints make a direct connection to practical concerns through a close correspondence with assertions, which are logical expressions that are checkable at runtime. Assertions state invariants that must be true for valid program execution. The ability to capture assertions in the same high-level language as the software they check lowers at least one barrier to adoption: the language barrier.

2) *Unit testing*: Testing offers a similarly low barrier to entry, requiring no training in the predicate calculus that undergirds formal methods. Most domain scientists focus on end-to-end tests that produce complex and comprehensive results in a given scientific domain. In aerodynamics, for example, such tests might compute fluid flow velocities over an extensive region of three-dimensional space so a researcher can verify the proper location of a shock wave over an airplane wing. On such a project, a research software engineer could add value by writing tests for individual program units such as the function that computes the jump in pressure across the shock wave at a given point in space. The term “unit testing” described such work at least as far back as 1997 when Zhu et al. [4] reviewed test adequacy measures across a quarter-century of testing research. Unit testing evaluates the correctness of code as fine-grained as a single function or branch.

Many projects employ continuous integration scripts to run unit tests automatically in response to each contribution of new code pushed to a software repository and each request to integrate new code into a repository branch. Thus, integration-time unit testing complements design-time constraint specification and runtime assertion checking. Although part of an informal approach to program evaluation, unit tests and assertions written in a standardized language are themselves formal to the extent that there exist formal definitions of the syntax and semantics in the language’s standard. The Fortran 2023 standard [5], for example, defines syntax rules in a variant of the Backus-Naur Form, a formal grammar used in the specification of several programming languages.

A sizable body of literature covers the testing of scientific software. In 2014, for example, Kanewala and Bieman [6] published a systematic literature review spanning 62 studies that provided information about testing scientific software. They identified 34 testing challenges in two broad groupings: challenges due to the characteristics of scientific software and challenges due to differences between the scientific and the software engineering community cultures. Among the challenges most relevant to the current study were several due to the aforementioned cultural differences:

- 1) The widespread use of Fortran made using many of the software engineering community’s testing tools difficult.
- 2) Unit testing is uncommon in science.
- 3) Scientists rarely have software engineering training.

TABLE I
FORTRAN UNIT TESTING SOFTWARE GITHUB DATA
(AS OF 15 MAY 2025)

Metric	Package Count	Package Names (if < 5)
Fortran > 70%	21	
Fortran \approx 100%	3	forunitest, Julienne, par-funnel
HEAD age < 12 months	9	
Archived (read-only)	1	funit
Organizationally hosted	3	Julienne, pFUnit, test-drive
Releases + tags > 0	11	
Contributors > 1	7	
Contributors \geq 5	2	pFUnit, test-drive, veggies
Commits > 100	4	FortUTF, Julienne pFUnit, veggies
User-defined operators	1	Julienne
Multi-image support	3	Julienne, pFUnit, Garden

Also in 2014, Clune et al. [7] reported reasons for the dearth of unit tests in climate models, an example of a community where Fortran is prevalent. The cited reasons included testing-framework language barriers and the large size of many software units (e.g., procedures): 1,000 lines. Given Fortran’s longstanding and continuing relevance in science and engineering [8], addressing the first gap above remains of great importance.

Much has changed in the intervening years with a burgeoning list of options for unit testing software written in and for Fortran. Beliaevsky’s “Fortran code on GitHub” list compiles 24 Fortran unit testing frameworks [9]. Although it is not clear that all on the list are general-purpose unit-testing utilities, Table I summarizes some observations from GitHub data. By the tabulated measures that arguably help to ensure longevity, only three projects are hosted by organizations, and only three have five or more contributors. As for measures that indicate ongoing development, nine have main branch HEAD commits dated within the preceding 12 months and only one package is fully dormant, i.e., archived and read-only. By one measure that helps to lower the barrier to use by Fortran programmers, 21 projects have more than 70% of their source code in Fortran, including three that GitHub describes as nearly 100% Fortran.

The bottom row of Table I shows support for executing multiple images — Fortran terminology for program instances that execute in parallel. The multi-image features, which have been part of Fortran since the 2008 standard [10], support Single-Program, Multiple-Data (SPMD) parallelism with a Partitioned Global Address Space (PGAS) for data distribution and communication [11]. Included in the bottom row is Garden, a veggies fork not included in Beliaevsky’s list. The bottom row includes pFUnit based on the work of Hassan et al. [12] in extending pFUnit to support multi-image execution.

3) *Assertions*: Assertions are a much smaller feature than unit tests in the sense that less code is generally needed to support them. In fact, with some languages including assertions as an intrinsic or standard library feature, assertions require no support other than the compiler. Of relevance in scientific computing, C and C++ provide assertion features.

TABLE II
FORTRAN ASSERTION UTILITY GITHUB DATA
(AS OF 15 MAY 2025)

Metric	Package Names
Fortran > 70%	Assert, fassert
Fortran = 100%	Assert, fassert
HEAD age < 12 months	Assert, fassert
Organizationally hosted	Assert
Releases + tags > 0	Assert, assert-fortran-git
Contributors > 1	Assert
Contributors \geq 5	Assert
Commits > 100	Assert, fassert
Pure procedure support	Assert, fassert
Multi-image support	Assert

Despite being a smaller feature, assertions have received considerable attention in the literature. The 2024 literature survey of assertions in software testing by Taramirad [13] covered 119 papers just from the prior two decades.

Even just focusing on Fortran, the assertions literature dates at least as far back as 1977, when Saib [14] discussed the role of executable assertions in static and dynamic program checks, detection of errors in input data, and proofs of correctness. Because runtime assertion checking and unit testing both address program correctness, unit testing frameworks sometimes include assertion capabilities. In such cases, testing frameworks often continue execution past assertion failures and tally the number success and failures. The assertions in the pFUnit, veggies, and Garden, for example, exhibit this behavior. By contrast, assertions in C and C++ are intended to address situations in which the program state precludes continuing, and thus generate a fatal error with an explanatory message.

Partly due to the compactness of this feature, only a few standalone runtime assertion utilities have been developed for Fortran. In addition to our Assert [15], we found two similar utilities: fassert [16] and assert-fortran-git [17]. Table II shows many of the same GitHub data for these three assertion utilities as Table I shows for testing frameworks.

4) *An origin story*: The veggies [18] unit-testing framework inspired our Julienne [19]. The internal organization of test-suite modules, the method for describing tests, and the structure of the test output all closely resemble those of veggies. Julienne started as barely more than 100 lines of source code designed as a temporary veggies substitute in order to work around compiler bugs that blocked the use of veggies with one vendor’s compiler. Julienne aimed to ensure portability across compilers through minimalism: the fewer required features, the lower the chance of a blocking compiler issue. The first inspiration for Julienne’s name thus comes from the term for vegetables sliced into thin strings: julienned vegetables.

Julienne currently supports the compilers listed in Table III. Because Julienne combines some language features from recent Fortran standards, supporting a compiler typically requires several cycles of compiler bug isolation and bug reporting, compiler fixes, and then retesting with patched compilers or new compiler releases. Work is underway to add support for the LFortran compiler with the first major milestone being that

TABLE III
JULIENNE 3.1.0 COMPILER SUPPORT

Vendor	Compiler	Version(s) Tested
GCC	gfortran	13.4.0, 14.3.0, 15.1.0
LLVM	flang-new	19, 20.1.8, 21.1.0
NAG	nagfor	7.2 Build 7235
Intel	ifx	2025.2.1 Build 20250806

the recent 3.0.2 release of Assert, Julienne’s only dependency, now supports LFortran.

Launched initially under the auspices of [Sourcery Institute](#), Julienne moved to the [GitHub organization for Lawrence Berkeley National Laboratory](#) within the first few months of development and became jointly copyrighted and licensed in August 2024. The 16 May 2025 initial submission of this paper happens to coincide with the one-year anniversary of the initial git commit in the [Julienne repository](#).

As the length of time increased for which Julienne was needed as a workaround, it became desirable to add features to Julienne. For example, Julienne initially lacked the ability to report diagnostic information detailing the nature of a test failure. Discussions around incorporating Julienne into the [Caffeine](#) [20] production compiler runtime library project partly influenced the decision to add such a capability. This capability was first added in a way that provided users several string-handling features to enable user-customized diagnostic messages from numeric data, including array data. The resultant expansion of support for string handling fit nicely with the project name and the aim to stay lightweight by offloading message construction responsibility to users.

Ultimately, the insights that most inspired this paper were realizing that Julienne could support novel idioms for expressing test criteria. In this new paradigm, a program expression, such as `i.isAtMost.j`, encapsulates a corresponding mathematical expression, $i \leq j$, and evaluates to a test-diagnosis object. The object encapsulates an indicator of whether the test passed. If and only if the test fails, the object also contains a diagnostic message generated by Julienne, automating the otherwise tedious task of string manipulation. In the course of writing this paper, it also became clear that the same idioms could be used to automate similar aspects of runtime assertion checking by providing a very thin wrapper around the Assert library’s `assert_always` procedure.

B. Objectives

This paper presents a new methodology for unit testing and assertion checking along with a set of unifying capabilities at the intersection thereof. The paper focuses on the approaches that Julienne supports. The objectives of the remainder of this paper are as follows: Sections II-A and II-B detail the expressive idioms that Julienne supports and the string-manipulation features that Julienne provides for constructing custom diagnostics as an alternative to the supported idioms. Sections II-C and III-D describe object-oriented design patterns that play central roles in writing and running tests and reporting the results. Sections III-A through III-E outline a demonstration

project in the Julienne repository and how to generate the demonstration project’s test suite using Julienne’s `scaffold` program. The generated scaffolding comprises a test-suite driver program and unit tests for the simple types and stub functions in the demonstration project. Section III-F describes the use of these technologies in a traditional high-performance computing application, Matcha, and a deep learning library, Fiats. Section IV concludes and discusses potential future work.

II. DESIGN

A. Expressive idioms

Among the widely used programming languages in computational science, Fortran offers a uniquely powerful yet underutilized facility for what the Fortran 2023 standard calls “defined operations.” Python and C++ allow programmers to overload those languages’ existing operators, Julia allows such overloading or suffixing existing operators, and C lacks any such capability. Conversely, Fortran enables users to overload existing operators (the “intrinsic” operators) **and** define new operators in the form of defined operations. In addition to enhancing code’s expressiveness, defining new operators increases code robustness by preventing the mistaken use of an overloaded operator in the place of a homonymous intrinsic operator. Defined operations have names with a leading and a trailing period (.) such as Julienne’s `.equalsExpected.` operator. Moreover, the English name of this operator implies a useful asymmetry: Julienne interprets `i.equalsExpected.j` to mean that `i` and `j` are the actual and expected values, respectively. Julienne labels the values accordingly when constructing a diagnostic message in the event that the expressed condition is not satisfied. Thus, natural language guides operator nomenclature.

Table IV lists some example expressions that Julienne 3.1.1 supports. Each listed expression evaluates to a `test_diagnosis_t` object that encapsulates an indicator of success or failure. If and only if the expression’s condition fails, the result object also contains an automatically constructed diagnostic message. The important advance that Julienne makes over common practice, however, lies in the automatic generation of the diagnostic message based on defined operations, some of which either have no intrinsic counterpart or have more meaning than their intrinsic counterpart.

Julienne exploits another capability that is unique to Fortran among popular computational science languages: almost all of the operators in Table IV are `elemental`, meaning the function defining the operator for scalar operands automatically applies to conformable array operands. Same-shaped array operands conform, as do scalar/array operand combinations. Thus, each operand in Table IV is defined by a function with scalar dummy arguments, but a user can apply a unary operator to an operand of rank of 0 (a scalar) through the highest standard rank: 15 (a 15-dimensional array).

For binary operators, each elemental operator thus supports 46 operand rank combinations:

- 1 for scalar operands,

TABLE IV
IDIOMS IN JULIENNE 3.1.1.

All operators are elemental except the `.all.` reduction operator. Please see the `test_diagnosis_t` [unit tests](#) for additional examples.

Row	Example expressions	Supported operand types of the bold operator
1	<code>x .approximates. y .within. tolerance</code>	real, double precision
2	<code>x .approximates. y .withinFraction. tolerance</code>	real, double precision
3	<code>x .approximates. y .withinPercentage. tolerance</code>	real, double precision
4	<code>.all. ([i,j] .lessThan. k)</code>	<code>test_diagnosis_t</code>
5	<code>.all. ([i,j] .lessThan. [k,m])</code>	<code>test_diagnosis_t</code>
6	<code>.all. (i .lessThan. [k,m])</code>	<code>test_diagnosis_t</code>
7	<code>(i .lessThan. j) .also. (k .equalsExpected. m)</code>	<code>test_diagnosis_t</code>
8	<code>x .lessThan. y</code>	integer, real, double precision
9	<code>x .greaterThan. y</code>	integer, real, double precision
10	<code>i .equalsExpected. j</code>	integer, character, <code>type(c_ptr)</code>
11	<code>i .isAtLeast. j</code>	integer, real, double precision
12	<code>i .isAtMost. j</code>	integer, real, double precision
13	<code>s .isBefore. t</code>	character
14	<code>s .isAfter. t</code>	character
15	<code>(.expect. allocated(A)) // '(expected an allocated array "A)'</code>	logical

TABLE V
STRING CONSTRUCTORS, MANIPULATION FUNCTIONS AND OPERATORS

Example expression	Result
<code>s%bracket()</code> , where <code>s=string_t("abc")</code>	<code>string_t("[abc]")</code>
<code>s%bracket("_")</code> , where <code>s=string_t("abc")</code>	<code>string_t("_abc_")</code>
<code>s%bracket("{","}")</code> , where <code>s=string_t("abc")</code>	<code>string_t("{abc}")</code>
<code>string_t(2)</code>	<code>string_t("2")</code>
<code>string_t(["a", "b", "c"])</code>	<code>[string_t("a"), string_t("b"), string_t("c")]</code>
<code>.cat. string_t([9,8,7])</code>	<code>string_t("987")</code>
<code>.csv. string_t([1.5,2.0,3.25])</code>	<code>string_t("1.50000000,2.00000000,3.25000000")</code>
<code>["do", "re", "mi"] .sv. " "</code>	<code>string_t("do re mi")</code>
<code>string_t("ab") // string_t("cd")</code>	<code>string_t("abcd")</code>
<code>"ab" // string_t("cd")</code>	<code>string_t("abcd")</code>
<code>string_t("ab") // "cd"</code>	<code>string_t("abcd")</code>

- 15 for array operands of equivalent rank 1-15,
- 15 for scalar/array operand combinations, and
- 15 for array/scalar combinations.

where scalar/array and array/scalar expressions behave as if the scalar is copied throughout a conformable array. This demonstrates the extreme conciseness of rank-agnostic programming using elemental procedures.

Array expressions yield array results. To define an acceptable test function, users can reduce an array result to a scalar with Julienne’s `.all.` operator. For example, consider the array expressions preceded by `.all.` in Table IV rows 4-6. The square brackets construct arrays. The condition in row 4 passes only if $i < k$ and $j < k$. The condition in row 5 passes only if $i < k$ and $j < m$. The condition in row 6 passes only if $i < k$ and $i < m$. The unary operator `.all.` produces diagnostic messages only for the array elements corresponding to failures.

For pairwise reductions, Julienne provides the `.also.` operator, defined as `.all. ([lhs,rhs])`, where `lhs` and `rhs` are the scalar left-hand- and right-hand-side operands with type `test_diagnosis_t`, respectively. Table IV row 7 shows an example expression using `.also.`, named to avoid any confusion that could arise from overloading its intrinsic logical equivalent: `.and.`. For similar reasons, Julienne defines `.lessThan.`, `.greaterThan.`,

`.isAtLeast.`, and `.isAtMost.` rather than overloading their intrinsic equivalents: `<`, `>`, `≥`, and `≤`.

The character examples in Table IV rows 13-14 demonstrate another minor benefit of the chosen nomenclature. The operators `.isBefore.` and `.isAfter.` more closely reflect natural language than how one typically translates their intrinsic counterparts `<` and `>` to natural language: “less than” and “greater than”, respectively.

Table IV row 15 shows an example expression with Julienne’s unary operator `.expect.`, which applies to logical (boolean) operands. This example uses the concatenation operator `//`, which prompts Julienne to append the subsequent string to the diagnostic messages.

B. Custom diagnostics

For test criteria that are not amenable to expression using the operators in Table IV, Julienne provides string-handling utilities to assist with crafting custom diagnostic messages. Table V show various string manipulations supported by Julienne’s `string_t` derived type. These include uses of the type-bound procedure `bracket`, the `string_t` constructors, the array-element-concatenation operator `.cat.`, the comma-separated-value operator `.csv.`, the separated-value operator `.sv.`, and the string-concatenation operator `//`.

```

1  interface julienne_assert
2      module procedure idiomatic_assert
3      module procedure logical_assert
4  end interface
5
6  interface call_julienne_assert_
7      pure module subroutine idiomatic_assert(test_diagnosis, file, line, description)
8          !! Error terminate if `test_diagnosis%test_passed() == .false.`
9          implicit none
10         type(test_diagnosis_t), intent(in) :: test_diagnosis
11         character(len=*), intent(in), optional :: file, description
12         integer, intent(in), optional :: line
13     end subroutine
14
15     pure module subroutine logical_assert(assertion, file, line, description)
16         !! Error terminate if `assertion == .false.`
17         implicit none
18         logical, intent(in) :: assertion
19         character(len=*), intent(in), optional :: file, description
20         integer, intent(in), optional :: line
21     end subroutine
22 end interface

```

Fig. 1. Generic interfaces `julienne_assert` and `call_julienne_assert_` for calling idiomatic and logical assertions.

Consider aggregating array expression results using the `.all.` operator. Each failed test, such as a failure of two operand array elements to match, generates a separate diagnostic message. This could be desirable if different elements represent different test categories. For example, one element might indicate success or failure in reading a file, whereas another element might indicate success or failure in comparing a computed numerical value to an expected value. Alternatively, consider a case in which each array expression element corresponds to the same category of test. For example, each element might result from comparing elements in two numerical arrays. In the case of a homogeneous testing category, it would likely be desirable to have one unified diagnostic message. Julienne’s string-handling features aid in constructing such a message.

C. Functional programming patterns

The software engineering literature often applies the term “syntactic sugar” to technologies analogous to Fortran’s defined operations and other languages’ overloaded or suffixed operators. The term is sometimes interpreted in ways that trivialize or even oppose the use of these features [21]. Referring to defined operations in a way that is purely syntactical misses the associated semantic requirements the feature imposes. For example, the Fortran standard requires that the dummy arguments associated with the defined operations’ operands must have the `intent(in)` attribute. By prohibiting side effects on the operands, such a requirement nudges a programmer in the direction of functional programming, a paradigm that prohibits all side effects.

Rouson et al. [22] outlined an approach that elevates side-effect-free functions to a central role in scientific programming. The approach involves writing partial differential equation solvers, for example, as repeated evaluations of expressions built up from composable defined operations. The operation is declared with Fortran’s `pure` attribute, a keyword intended to convey the absence of side effects. Side effects include any modifications of the program’s state other than mapping inputs to outputs using local data declared within the procedure and not saved when the procedure terminates.

The idioms defined in Section II-A adapt the Rouson et al. approach to the program correctness-checking domain. Every function that implements every operator described Section II-A in Julienne is implicitly or explicitly `pure`. The explicit cases have the `pure` keyword in the function interface body. The implicit cases are functions that instead have the `elemental` attribute, which designates such functions as implicitly `pure` unless their interfaces include the keyword `impure`.

D. Assertions

Julienne offers thin wrappers around the Assert library, bringing the expressive idioms of section II-A to the otherwise disparate domain of runtime assertions. Doing so relies on a fortunate correspondence between the two domains. Julienne’s test functions produce a `test_diagnosis_t` object result that encapsulates information that very nearly matches Assert’s required subroutine arguments: a `logical` outcome indicator and a `character` string that serves as the stop code in an `error stop` statement that executes when an assertion fails.

```

0 $ cat test/assertion_failure_demo.F90
1 #include "julienne-assert-macros.h"
2 program assertion_failure_demo
3  !! Demonstrate a failing idiomatic assertion
4  use julienne_m, only : call_julienne_assert_, operator(.equalsExpected.)
5  implicit none
6  print '(a)', 'Testing intentional failure of idiomatic assertion:'
7  call_julienne_assert(2+2 .equalsExpected. 5)
8 end program
9
10 $ fpm test --compiler flang-new assertion_failure_demo --flag -DASSERTIONS
11 <build output elided...>
12 Testing intentional failure of idiomatic assertion:
13 Fortran ERROR STOP: Assertion failure at ./test/assertion_failure_demo.F90:7:
14 call_julienne_assert(2+2 .equalsExpected. 5)
15 expected 5; actual value is 4
16 <ERROR> Execution for object " assertion_failure_demo " returned exit code 1
17 <ERROR> *cmd_run*:stopping due to failed executions
18 STOP 1

```

Fig. 2. Demonstration of `call_julienne_assert` usage with an idiomatic condition and assertion failure output

Figure 1 shows Julienne’s two assertion wrapper interfaces, both of which initiate error termination if the provided assertion condition fails:

- 1) The `julienne_assert` generic interface is intended to be called directly and unconditionally enforces the assertion using the Assert library, whereas
- 2) The `call_julienne_assert_` generic interface is intended for invocation via the preprocessor macro `call_julienne_assert`, which enforces the condition when assertions are globally enabled.

In a build where assertions are globally disabled (e.g. for performance of production runs), the function-like macro invocation `call_julienne_assert(cond)` expands to nothing. When assertions are globally enabled, it expands to call `call_julienne_assert_(cond)`, which in turn calls the Assert library to enforce the condition.¹

The two aforementioned generic interfaces share the same two corresponding specific subroutines:

- 1) `idiomatic_assert` has a `test_diagnosis_t` dummy argument as its only non-optional argument, whereas
- 2) `logical_assert` has a `logical` dummy argument as its only non-optional argument.

When invoked via the preprocessor macro with only the one required argument, the preprocessor constructs and inserts the other arguments appropriately. It is intended that both subroutines will be invoked with an expression as the actual

¹The unfortunate nomenclature difference between the macro and the corresponding generic interface, wherein the latter has a trailing underscore, works around unfriendly behavior in the `gfortran` preprocessor (which crashes if a function-like macro expands to a token list that contains the macro name). In such circumstances, the C preprocessor standard mandates silent truncation of further expansion to prevent infinite recursion.

argument corresponding to the non-optional dummy argument. The `idiomatic_assert` subroutine gets a diagnostic string from its `test_diagnosis_t` dummy argument and includes this string in the stop code of the error stop statement that executes if a given assertion fails.

Figure 2 demonstrates a simple program using Julienne assertions. The top half of the figure shows the program code. Line 1 activates Julienne’s preprocessor macro support and line 4 imports the relevant symbols from the `julienne_m` module. Line 7 shows an invocation of the `call_julienne_assert` function-like macro, with an idiomatic conditional expression. Line 10 shows the Fortran Package Manager (`fpm` [23]) command to build and run this program with conditional assertions enabled (`--flag -DASSERTIONS`), and lines 13-15 show the resulting `ERROR STOP` output from the failed assertion. Notice this failure message includes the file name and line number identifying the location of the failed assertion (line 13), a literal copy of the failed assertion expression as represented in the source code (line 14), and the evaluated values of the operands for the failed `.equalsExpected.` operator (line 15). Thus, the concise, natural-language expression of a program invariant on line 7 has automatically led to a wealth of useful debugging information output to the console upon failure detection.

III. DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

A. Julienne’s demonstration project

Generating, perusing, and using the demonstration project in Julienne’s demo subdirectory illustrates the Julienne approach to writing unit tests. Figure 3 shows the contents of the demo directory tree, where `fpm.toml` is an `fpm` manifest (build system), the `src` directory contains modules defining a very

```
demo
|-- fpm.toml: fpm manifest (build system)
|-- README.md: documentation
|-- src
|   |-- specimen_m.f90: module with stubs
|   |-- widget_m.f90: module with stubs
|
|-- test
|   |-- driver.f90: test main program
|   |-- specimen_test_m.f90: test module
|   |-- widget_test_m.f90: test module
|
|-- test-suite.json
```

Fig. 3. Contents of the Julienne demo directory.

simple software library, and the `test` subdirectory contains test-suite driver program plus two supporting modules that the driver uses to test the code in the `src` subdirectory.

The `src` directory modules `specimen_m` and `widget_m` have identical contents except for the names of the derived types they contain: `specimen_t` and `widget_t`, respectively. Each of the latter two derived types has one type-bound function `pi` that defines results corresponding to a reference approximation for the mathematical constant π . Julienne’s scaffold program automatically generated the boilerplate code in the `test` subdirectory that checks two other π approximations against the reference value produced by each type’s `pi` function.

B. Test scaffolding

Creating a JavaScript Object Notation (JSON) file with the following contents instructs Julienne’s scaffold program to create the contents of the `test` subdirectory:

```
{
  "test suite": {
    "test subjects": ["specimen", "widget"]
  }
}
```

which matches the `test-suite.json` file in the repository except for blank-space edits. To create different project scaffolding, a Julienne user need only modify the elements in the `test subjects` array.

With the above `test-suite.json` file location and contents, running the following command from the `demo/README.md` file generates simple, working test modules `specimen_test_m` and `widget_test_m`:

```
fpm run scaffold \
  --compiler flang-new \
  -- --json-file demo/test-suite.json \
  --suite-path demo/test
```

Alternatively, one can replace `flang-new` with one of the other compilers listed in the `demo/README.md` file. This same command causes scaffold to automatically generate a test-suite driver program.

C. Demonstration test-suite driver program and output

Figure 4 shows the generated driver program stored in the Julienne demo repository. Lines 7-9 construct a test harness from an array of text fixtures, each constructed by invoking a test structure constructor. This arrangement effectively constructs a polymorphic array of tests. Each test must be an instance of a concrete derived type that extends Julienne’s `test_t` abstract type. At line 11, the driver runs all tests and reports results. The `demo/README.md` file provides fpm commands for running the driver using each of the supported compilers. For example, in the `demo` directory, the command:

```
fpm test \
  --compiler flang-new --flag -O3 \
  -- --contains string_t
```

builds the demonstration test suite with the LLVM Flang compiler and runs only the tests with subjects or descriptions containing `"string_t"`.

Figure 5 shows the demonstration project’s test output, omitting some heading and trailing information. Lines 1 and 10 name the test subjects. Lines 2-6 and 11-16 report test passes, failures, skips, and what each test does. For failures, the output contains automatically-generated diagnostic information (from expected through 3.142857074738). Appended to the generated text is a user-supplied message in parentheses.

Julienne’s mechanism for skipping tests facilitates porting across compilers: if a test crashes when built with a given compiler, skipping the test with that compiler allows subsequent tests to execute. Skipped-test output also documents which features the project cannot support with the chosen compiler.

D. Test reporting: A parallel Template Method pattern

Central to the generated test-suite driver lies an invocation of the test harness’s `report_results` type-bound procedure at line 11 in Figure 4. This procedure embodies a Template Method Object-Oriented Design (OOD) pattern [24]. In OOD, a class implements a Template Method by defining a procedure that invokes unimplemented procedure interfaces: “deferred bindings” in Fortran terminology. These deferred bindings collectively outline an algorithm’s steps.

At the top level, this process starts with calling the test harness’s `report_results` procedure, which calls a `report` procedure (not shown) on each element in the harness’s component `test_fixture_t` array. Each text fixture has a polymorphic `test_t` component on which the fixture invokes a `report` procedure. The `test_t` parent’s `report` procedure in turn invokes the subject and results bindings (which are implemented on a child type such as the `specimen_test_t` type in Figure 6. This cascade of calls produces the test output in lines 1-8 of Figure 5.

Because Julienne supports Fortran’s multi-image parallel features, the `test_harness_t` type’s `report_results` procedure and the `test_t` type’s `report` procedure are explicitly parallel and bulk synchronous. Each ensures that only one image produces driver-program output. Moreover, the `report` procedure uses the result of a collective reduction to

```

1 program test_suite_driver
2   use julienne_m, only : test_fixture_t, test_harness_t
3   use specimen_test_m, only : specimen_test_t
4   use widget_test_m, only : widget_test_t
5   implicit none
6
7   associate(test_harness => test_harness_t([ &
8     test_fixture_t(specimen_test_t()) &
9     ,test_fixture_t(widget_test_t()) &
10  ]))
11     call test_harness%report_results
12   end associate
13 end program test_suite_driver

```

Fig. 4. Contents of `demo/test/driver.f90`, the test-suite driver program generated automatically by the `app/scaffold` application using the `demo/test-suite.json` input file.

```

1 A specimen
2   passes on doing something.
3   FAILS on checking something.
4     diagnostics:
5       expected 3.141592741013 within a tolerance of 0.1000000047497E-02;
6       actual value is 3.142857074738 (pi approximation)
7   SKIPS on skipping something.
8 1 of 3 tests passed. 1 tests were skipped.
9
10 A widget
11 passes on doing something.
12 FAILS on checking something.
13 diagnostics:
14 expected 3.141592741013 within a tolerance of 0.1000000047497E-02;
15 actual value is 3.142857074738 (pi approximation)
16 SKIPS on skipping something.
17 1 of 3 tests passed. 1 tests were skipped.
18
19 _____ 2 of 6 tests passed. 2 tests were skipped _____

```

Fig. 5. Output from the Julienne repository’s demonstration project test suite with blank-space adjustments for presentation.

report a test as passing or skipped only if it passed or was skipped on all images. If a Julienne assertion fails on any image, the image executes an `error stop` statement, which halts all images.

E. Demonstration test module

Figure 6 lists a demonstration test module, including

- Lines 8-12 define the required test type, `specimen_test_t`, which, as a concrete child of the `test_t` abstract type, must define two type-bound procedures:
 - A subject function at lines 16-19 produces the text in line 1 of Figure 5 and
 - A results function at lines 21-29, the result of which is a `test_result_t` array defined by assign-
- ing the result of the inherited `run` function, provided a `test_description_t` array argument.
- Each `test_description_t` object at lines 25-27 is an invocation of a constructor that takes two arguments:
 - a character description, the test function, and
 - optionally, the described test function’s name, which if omitted as at line 27, causes the test to be skipped.
- Test functions must have no arguments and must define a `test_diagnosis_t` result.

The `do_something` and `check_something` test functions in Figure 6 demonstrate the two ways of constructing a test diagnosis:

- 1) Lines 34-36 use a Julienne idiom based on the operators `.all.`, `.approximates.`, `.within.`, and `//`.
- 2) Line 42 invokes a `test_diagnosis_t` constructor.

```

1 module specimen_test_m
2   use julienne_m, only : &
3     test_t, test_description_t, test_diagnosis_t, test_result_t &
4     , operator(.approximates.), operator(.within.), operator(.all.), operator(//)
5   use specimen_m, only : specimen_t
6   implicit none
7
8   type, extends(test_t) :: specimen_test_t
9   contains
10    procedure, nopass :: subject
11    procedure, nopass :: results
12  end type
13
14 contains
15
16  pure function subject() result(test_subject)
17    character(len=:), allocatable :: test_subject
18    test_subject = 'A specimen'
19  end function
20
21  function results() result(test_results)
22    type(specimen_test_t) specimen_test
23    type(test_result_t), allocatable :: test_results(:)
24    test_results = specimen_test%run( &
25      [test_description_t('doing something', do_something) &
26        ,test_description_t('checking something', check_something) &
27        ,test_description_t('skipping something') &
28      ])
29  end function
30
31  function check_something() result(test_diagnosis)
32    type(test_diagnosis_t) test_diagnosis
33    type(specimen_t) specimen
34    test_diagnosis = .all.( &
35      [22./7., 3.14159] .approximates. specimen%pi() .within. 0.001 &
36    ) // ' (pi approximation)'
37  end function
38
39  function do_something() result(test_diagnosis)
40    type(test_diagnosis_t) test_diagnosis
41    test_diagnosis = &
42      test_diagnosis_t(test_passed = 1 == 1, diagnostics_string = 'craziness ensued')
43  end function
44
45 end module

```

Fig. 6. A demonstration test module from Julienne's demo/test directory defining the specimen_test_t type.

The `.approximates.` and `.within.` operators check to see whether the actual values differ from the expected value by more than the provided tolerance. Because the actual values are in a two-element array on the left of line 35 in Figure 6, the expression on that line evaluates to an array of two `test_diagnosis_t` objects. The `.all.` operator aggregates these into one `test_diagnosis_t` object that represents a passing test only if all array components pass. During the aggregation process, Julienne reports diagnostic information only for failing tests. Optionally, each diagnostic message can include trailing text that the user provides via the concatenation operator `//`.

F. Tests and assertions in Fiats and Matcha

Given the recent vintage of the Julienne framework, the authors are engaged in an ongoing process of integrating Julienne into our other projects. Work is also underway with external collaborators who are integrating Julienne into their projects. Additionally, the authors have taught tutorials on unit testing with Julienne [25].

Furthest along in the process of adoption are the `Fiats` deep learning library [26] and the `Matcha` T-cell motility simulator [27]. Both use Julienne and `Assert`. `Matcha` contains 7 tests in its test suite, and 27 assertions across its `app`, `example`, `src` and `test` subdirectories. `Fiats` contains 22 tests and 114 assertions across its `demo`, `src` and `test` subdirectories. Julienne itself contains 37 tests in its own test suite and 4 tests in a demonstration project subdirectory. Julienne contains 204 assertions across its `example`, `src` and `test` subdirectories.

The `Fiats` and `Matcha` tests all use Julienne’s custom-diagnostic construction described in Section II-B. Assertions in `Fiats` and `Matcha` currently all invoke the `Assert` library directly. Therefore, `Fiats` and `Matcha` both offer relatively straightforward migration paths to the new idiomatic forms of correctness-checking that this paper describes. The transition will require no change in the project dependencies, no changes to the file or module structure, and the transition can happen incrementally.

IV. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

This paper demonstrates idioms that afford writing expressions inspired by natural language in unit tests and assertions. The test expressions evaluate to test-diagnosis objects that contain pass/fail test-outcome information along with automatically generated diagnostic messages. The presented approach leverages Fortran 2023 to implement a Template Method `OOD` pattern, to support multi-image parallel execution, and to support functional programming patterns while allowing for rich diagnostic output from `pure` procedures when assertions fail.

This paper also provides an overview of a demonstration project in the Julienne repository and how to use Julienne’s `scaffold` utility to generate the scaffolding for a test suite in the demonstration project.

Finally, the paper also reports on the progress with integrating these technologies into the `Fiats` deep learning library and the `Matcha` scientific application. The paper details the extent to which the Julienne unit testing framework and `Assert` library have been adopted by `Fiats` and `Matcha`. The paper also describes a path for integrating the new idiomatic correctness-checking approach into both client packages. Future work will involve traversing that path and building upon the new approach.

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ACRONYMS

JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
OCL	Object Constraint Language
OOD	Object-Oriented Design
PGAS	Partitioned Global Address Space
SPMD	Single-Program, Multiple-Data
UML	Unified Modeling Language

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